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BEESSNESS ACTIONS OF THE ECOTOXICOLOGY AND LANDSCAPE GROUP - UNIOESTE: SO FAR AND SO CLOSE

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Abstract

Within the BEESSNESS project goals, the Ecotoxicology and Landscape Research Group at the State University of West Parana aimed to evaluate the effects of anthropogenic actions on bee communities in the Caatinga from a macro (geospatial – landscape) and a micro (biomarkers – organisms) perspective. In addition, it also participated in ecotoxicological tests conducted with different bee species exposed to different pesticides used in fruit crops. Through the identification of bees collected from specific points in the Caatinga, as well as the joining of occurrence points obtained from citizen science databases^{1,2}, it was possible to verify the interference of

deforestation and fire events in the Caatinga on the richness of bee species, with intense dominance of *Apis mellifera* in high anthropised areas. By evaluating the health status of bees collected in areas with different pressures, a similar result was observed: high anthropogenic disturbance led to greater oxidative damage and neurotoxic reactions. In addition, different exchange activities were held with the Insecta Group at UFRB. UNIOESTE students travelled to Cruz das Almas, BA, and conducted experimental activities, while UFRB students visited UNIOESTE and conducted laboratory activities for analysing antioxidant activities, oxidative stress analyses, neurotoxicity evaluations, and bee energy reserves. This exchange made it possible to identify dose-response relationships and understand animals' energy metabolism when exposed to different pesticides entering different exposure routes. The activities carried out so far within the Caatinga allowed us to understand the dynamics of bee communities in such a peculiar biome, with extensive commercial productivity but threatened by human action in the excessive use of agrochemicals. So far physically, but so close in the action of environmental conservation.

References

Global Biodiversity Information Facility – GBIF. Available in <https://www.gbif.org>

Species Link. Available in <https://specieslink.net/>

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